

IMPACT OF AUDITING AND TAXATION ON SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE BUSINESS PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM FIRM – LEVEL DATA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of auditing and taxation on the performance of small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria, utilising World Bank 2025 firm-level data for Nigeria and applying both robust Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) and Instrumental Variable - Two-Stage Least Squares (IV-2SLS) regression models for robustness checks. The findings revealed robust and consistent model results of the determining factors, with both auditing and taxation variables being significantly associated with small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. While auditing and tax audit visits or meeting consistently showed positive and statistically significant influence, delays in receiving final audit reports was found to be significantly negatively influencing small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. Further, taxation-connected variables largely showed robust and consistent negative significant influence on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. It was recommended however that government and its policymakers need to enhance and simplify auditing procedures, reassess tax audit systems, reform tax and tax administration policies, among others.

Keywords: Auditing; Taxation; Small and medium scale businesses; Nigeria; Enterprise Survey; SMEs, robust OLS; IV-2SLS model.

JEL Codes: C1, D9, H0, H2, H3, O17, O55

1. INTRODUCTION

Small and medium scale businesses form the main pillar of Nigerian economy. These businesses are vital forces behind technical advancement, industrialization, employment creation, and sustainable growth and development of the economy (Odebode, Salisu, Shokunbi, & Oladayo-Ibrahim, 2019; Eteng, Numaliya, Antuwa, & Richards, 2025). In the year 2025, the small and medium scale businesses accounted for roughly 84% of all jobs in Nigeria and have generated around 48% of the country's GDP, hence making these businesses a significant part of the country's economy (Agusto & Co., 2025; Moniepoint, 2025; Chimenka, Regidor, Adeniyi, & Murtadho, 2025).

Small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria function in a turbulent environment marked by inadequate infrastructure, restricted access to financing, and intricate regulatory frameworks, notwithstanding their substantial socioeconomic significance (Endris & Kassegn, 2022; Omeje, Mba, & Rena, 2024; Olayeye, 2025). These businesses encounter a number of difficulties that impair their general performance, output, and/or performance (Enang, Alexander, Faleye, 2022; Inegbedion & Okoye-uzu, 2024). Among these difficulties, the combined impact of auditing and taxation stand out as the key factors influencing their efficiency and performance level (Inegbedion & Okoye-uzu, 2024). For instance, auditing which serves as an instrument for ensuring openness and accountability, and as such, boosts confidence in business or enterprise operations, thereby creating more opportunities in making more finance accessible, has not been duly followed or implemented by these small and medium scale businesses. A look at Figure 1 shows the distribution of small and medium scale businesses that have indulged in auditing of their businesses and those that have even attended tax audit meetings as reported by World Bank (2025).

Fig.1: Auditing and Tax Audit Meetings among Small & Medium Scale Businesses in Nigeria

Source: World Bank (2025) Nigerian Enterprise Survey data

Figure 1 demonstrates that the implementation of auditing practices among small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria has been very low. For instance, out of 1043 small and medium scale businesses surveyed, only 37% (391) of them agreed that they audited their business (yes), whereas 62% (645) of them disagreed auditing their business (no), while 1% (7) of these businesses do not know what auditing is all about (don't know). Again, out of 644 small and medium scale businesses that responded on attending tax audit meetings, few of them, representing 30% (192) agreed that they attended tax audit meetings (yes), whereas 67% (430) of these businesses did not attend any form of tax audit meetings (no), while 3% (22) of them do not even know anything about attending tax audit meetings.

Further, taxation has been seen as a policy that helps governments to get finances needed for the smooth running of the government, and that which is needed for infrastructural and economic growth and development of the economy (Enang, Alexander, & Faleye, 2022). However, even though taxation is necessary to generate funds for the government to enable it carry out these governmental functions, high taxation rates usually pose as obstacle to small

and medium scale businesses, and this often impede smooth business operations and as such, discourage investment and performance of these enterprises (Olayeye, 2025; Dixon, Smulders, & Odendaal, 2024; Omeje, Uchendu, & Rena, 2024). For example, Figure 2 below presents the ditribution of small and medium scale businesses with taxation and tax administration experiences in Nigeria. The case here is on whether taxation and tax administration in Nigeria are seen and/or percieved by small and medium scale businesses as obstacle(s) to their business or not.

Fig.2: Tax and Tax Administration Experiences among Small & Medium Scale Businesses in Nigeria

Source: World Bank (2025) Nigerian Enterprise Survey data

Figure 2 indicates that while majority of these small and medium scale businesses, 99.42% (i.e. 1037 out of 1043) agreed that taxation in Nigeria is an obstacle to their businesses (yes), very few of them, 0.48% (i.e. 5 out of 1043) disagreed that taxation in Nigeria is an obstacle to their businesses (no), and a mere 0.10% (i.e. 1 out of 1043) of these businesses do not know whether taxation is an obstacle to their businesses or not (don't know). With respect to tax administration, a vast majority of these businesses, 99.33% (1036 out of 1043) accepted that tax administration in Nigeria constitutes an obstacle to their businesses (yes), just very few of them, 0.48% (i.e. 5 out of 1043) disagreed that tax administration in Nigeria forms an obstacle to their businesses (no), and whereas a mere 0.19% (i.e. 2 out of 1043) of them do not know if tax administration in Nigeria constitutes an obstacle to their businesses (don't know).

It is worth noting here therefore, that depending on the business characteristics like size, industry or sector, and management style, the impact of auditing and taxation, and other determining factors like access to finance, insecurity, ownership structure of the business, time spent on dealing with government regulations by managers, and even customs and trade regulation could make small and medium scale business performance to vary (Omeje, Mba, & Rena, 2024; Ugwu & Omeje, 2021; Eteng, *et al.*, 2025). Even as the performance of these small and medium scale businesses could vary because of these factors, the impact of auditing and taxation on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria remain underexplored, and as such, the quest for this current study.

This study therefore seeks to utilizing firm-level data and econometric model, with Instrumental Variable – Two Stage Least Squares (IV – 2SLS) model for robustness checks, to examine the impact of auditing and taxation on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria since available literature in this area with respect to Nigeria mainly focused only on either auditing or taxation in isolation. Some of these literature have individually concentrated on how tax arrangements or policies, tax administration, tax audit, multiple taxation, among others influence SMEs survival, profits, performance, performance, and/or compliance behaviours in a given State without considering the whole country (Olayeye, 2025; Agbaje, Bojuwon, & Abidoeye, 2017; Chimenka, Regidor, Adeniyi, & Murtadho, 2025; Udeh, Odion, & Izevbekhai, 2022; Eteng, Numaliya, Antuwa, and Richards, 2025), while others have focused on how tax compliance and its costs, tax auditing, tax rates, value added taxation (VAT), and even multiple taxation levied among small and medium scale businesses impact profitability, performance, or growth of these businesses (Olasupo, Sorunke, & Olawuyi, 2016; Ndlovu & Schutte, 2026; Scholtz & Laing, 2024; Marivate, 2024). However, these studies have not simultaneously looked at the impact of auditing and taxation on these small and medium scale business in Nigeria as a whole using the current (2025) firm level data for the country. Therefore, in view of this, the current study modestly serves as an extension and/or consolidation of existing literature in this area since few empirical studies have been conducted in this area, even as none of these existing literature has used nationally represented firm level data to concurrently examine the impact of both auditing and taxation on performance of small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria. This study seeks to bridge this study gap by providing empirical evidence on how these two critical factors interact to shape the performance of these small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

Theoretical literature that forms the framework of this study is based on the agency-deterrence integration theory. Since this study focuses on unravelling the impact of auditing and taxation on small and medium scale business performance, the most robust approach is to integrate agency theory with economic deterrence theory of taxation. These theories are briefly examined below:

A. Agency Theory from Auditing Viewpoint

This theory was propounded by Jensen and Meckling (1976). It was further developed by Fama (1980), Fama and Jensen (1983), and Eisenhardt (1989). This theory has been applied by Watts and Zimmerman (1986; 1990) in auditing and accounting in which they advanced the ‘positive accounting theory’ that describes how businesses willingly select a particular auditing and accounting procedures in order to save agency costs. The agency paradigm also known as the agency theory, is utilised to comprehend relationships in which one party (the principal/owners/shareholders) assigns tasks or decision-making power to another party (the agent/managers).

With regard for auditing, this theory offers a solid justification for the role, presence, and continuous need of independent or autonomous audits to help reduce information irregularity and interest clashes (Eisenhardt, 1989; Watts & Zimmerman, 1986; 1990; Adams, 1994; Mustapha & Yaen, 2015). This theory emphasizes the significance of auditing in lowering information irregularity/gap and as well, guarantee accountability, which can boost business performance (Adams, 1994). The relevance of this theory to this current study as it relates to SMEs performance is that even though SMEs ownership and its management may intersect,

there may still be associated agency costs with outside parties or stakeholders such as banks and tax agencies (Mustapha & Yaen, 2015), and by eliminating information irregularity/gap, auditing acts as a monitoring tool that improves resource distribution and lowers investment costs, which immediately enhance SMEs performance. Again, by ensuring that agents or managers of SMEs behave in the principals'/owners'/shareholders' best interests, auditing may improve small and medium scale business performance (Mustapha & Yaen, 2015).

B. Economic Deterrence Theory from Taxation Viewpoint

This theory was propounded by Allingham and Sandmo (1972). It is sometimes called as the Allingham-Sandmo model. This theory was further developed and applied by Sandmo (2005), Alm (2012), Coolidge (2012), Slemrod (2019), among others. The theory posits that taxpayers are 'rational evaders' who balance the advantages of tax evasion against the likelihood of being discovered (audit probability) and the gravity of the penalties involved (Allingham & Sandmo, 1972; Alm, 2012; Slemrod, 2019). This theory clarifies how people make decisions about tax evasion and as such, it predicated on the cost-benefit trade-off method, in which people balance the possible advantages of tax evasion with respect to the costs associated with identification and penalties (Allingham & Sandmo, 1972; Coolidge, 2012; Slemrod, 2019). In this model, SMEs make business choices expected to maximize their performance or utility given the income they have reported, bearing in mind that they are risk neutral. The model takes into account the effects of rates of taxation, evasion fines, and the likelihood of being discovered by tax agencies (Sandmo, 2005; Coolidge, 2012; Slemrod, 2019).

Therefore, the proposition of the agency-deterrence integration theory with respect to the impact of auditing and taxation on small and medium scale business performance is that auditing should encourage small and medium scale business performance through the enhancement of financial transparency and accountability (agency), where auditing and taxation threats deter non-compliance, thereby reducing performance costs that are tied to the penalties or reputational damage (Allingham & Sandmo, 1972; Slemrod, 2019). In fact, this agency-deterrence integration theory argues that auditing and taxation drive small and medium scale businesses to be more efficient and compliant, thereby creating room for performance enhancement.

The relevance of the agency-deterrence integration theory to this current study as it connects to small and medium scale business performance is that auditing serves as a constraint and/or deterrent, such that when SMEs are audited, they become more likely to abide by tax regulations. An equitable and transparent tax audit arrangement can lessen participants' or SMEs 'informal economy' advantage to evade tax, thereby, promoting adequate financial record keeping, profitable investment, and increased performance, even in the presence of high taxation that has the potential of depleting SMEs resources.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Empirically, there exist scanty literature on the impact of auditing and taxation on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. Related domestic studies have either looked at how tax arrangements or policies, tax administration, tax audit, multiple taxation, among others influence SMEs survival, profits, performance, performance, and/or compliance behaviours. Hence, none of these domestic studies has simultaneously looked at the impact of auditing and taxation on small and medium scale business. The few related domestic studies reviewed include the study by Olayeye (2025) who used survey data generated from 10 SMEs in Akure South of Ondo state, Nigeria, descriptive analysis, and multiple regression model to examine how top administrators see tax arrangements and how these arrangements influence their business profits and performance. It was shown by the study that that majority of these top

administrators see Nigerian tax policies or arrangements as having less effective impact on their business profits and performance. Agbaje, Bojuwon, and Abidoye (2017) utilised similar survey data obtained from 120 small and medium scale businesses and applied probit model to investigate how audit services and proper account records influence the performance of small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Ogun State, Nigeria. It was indicated that that SMEs performances were significantly encouraged by appropriate audit and comprehensive account reports. In addition, Chimenka, Regidor, Adeniyi, and Murtadho (2025) employed survey data, descriptive, and multiple regression model to establish that in Ogun State, SMEs profitability of has been encouraged and has been considerably impacted by tax inducements and tax uses, and that tax collection has considerable negative impact. Based on the results, the study suggested that Ogun State's tax arrangements need to be developed to support SMEs growth and sustainability. Bassey, Amoke, and Oha (2025) adopted survey data obtained from 400 MSMEs in Cross River State, Nigeria and logit model to demonstrate that financial factors insignificantly and inversely influence the performance of MSMEs in the State.

Udeh, Odion, and Izevbekhai (2022) also in a similar study tried to determine in South-South States, Nigeria, how multiple tax system influence SMEs growth through the application of survey data and multiple regression model. It was discovered that while consumption and infrastructural development taxes had positive significant influence on SMEs growth, environmental and sanitation taxes, and property and land-based taxation have meaningful negative influence on SMEs growth in the economy. Similarly, Ocheni and Gemade (2015) utilised survey data, descriptive statistics, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) to investigate in Benue State, how multiple taxes influence survival of SMEs. Finding showed that SMEs survival is significantly and negatively impacted by multiple taxation, with substantial influence on SMEs' size and their capacity to tax payments. It was suggested that the government need to adopt consistent tax laws that would support the growth of SMEs in the State and Nigeria at large, while taking SMEs size into account. Omeje, Mba, and Ugwu (2022), and Eteng, Numaliya, Antuwa, and Richards (2025) adopted logit model and survey data obtained from 400 SMEs in 5 Nigerian States to analyse in Nigeria, how SMEs credit performance and tax obedience were being impacted by multiple taxation. It was shown by the study that there exists strong negative link between tax obedience and multiple taxation, with negative significant impact of multiple taxation on SME credit performance in the economy. Further, there exist large and disorganized tax burdens significantly lower SMEs profitability, deter corporate reinvestment, and raise the risk of tax disobedience and/or non-compliance. It was recommended among others by the study that in order to encourage SME growth and credit sustainability, there is need for government and its tax agencies to develop a harmonized or coherent tax system, improved education of taxpayers, and tax administration platform with single window.

In an effort to find out how business performance SMEs are being influenced by good accounting reports, Umar (2019) used survey data and ANOVA to establish that maintaining the required or adequate accounting records or reports would boost lenders and creditors trust or confidence in the SMEs ability to get funding. However, inappropriate accounting records and/or reporting was found to be bringing significant strain or difficulty on the SMEs auditing and financial inspection. Again, Inegbedion and Okoye-uzu (2024) applied structural equation model and survey data collected from 205 SMEs managers and owners in Nigeria to study how tax audits and tax obedience impact tax incomes. It was discovered that tax obedience is encouraged significantly by field and desk tax auditing, and that tax income is significantly encouraged by field and desk taxation audits, and tax obedience in the economy. Further finding indicated the existence of strong association between tax auditing, tax obedience and tax incomes emanating from SMEs in the country. Ojo and Shittu (2023) employed panel data

collected from 3,600 SMEs and which spans from 2018 – 2022, with multiple regression model based on Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) technique to determine among SMEs in Nigeria, what value added tax (VAT) compliance factors could be. It was revealed that VAT compliance is significantly determined by such factors like the attitudes and understanding of taxpayers, cost of tax obedience or compliance, operational efficiency of VAT, and business characteristics. Again, SMEs VAT compliance was found to be significantly encouraged by the degree, size and/or magnitude of profit made by these businesses. Abdullahi (2025) applied time series data spanning 2000 to 2024 and Tobit model to reveal that informal sector size, mean income, and financial services access strongly enhance tax revenue from the sector, whereas rise in employment level discourages tax revenue in the country.

Further, the study by Kings (2018) adopted survey data and descriptive statistics to analyse in Nigeria, how auditing in SMEs could influence their growth using a case of Albertina Nigeria Ltd. It was demonstrated by the study that auditing in SMEs has positive significant influence on their growth processes. The study therefore suggested appropriate administration and auditing of cash inflows and outflows in a bid to encourage or boost business growth. Again, there is need for an improved internal audit and control system for SMEs efficiency, growth and sustainability. Nnam, Maduabuchi, Igwe, Okeke, and Chukwunwike (2022) used OLS-based multiple regression analysis and survey data to find out whether taxation significantly impacts SMEs growth, with a focus on cash flows, profitability, and investment choices. Findings revealed that there exists significant impact of taxation on SMEs cash flows, profitability, and investment choices in the country. To enhance SMEs growth therefore, the study suggested that government must ensure enhanced tax inducement, provision of more infrastructure, adoption of ability to pay tax law, and shunning all forms of multiple taxation on SMEs. Omeje, Chukwu, Mba, and Ugwu (2024), and Olasupo, Sorunke, and Olawuyi (2016) tried to establish how SMEs performance is affected by financial inclusion, and constitutional auditing through the adoption of descriptive statistics and survey data generated from 100 SMEs and 25 accountants. It was therefore established that SMEs constitutional auditing has been severely hampered by lack of adequate accounting mechanism and comprehensive records of financial activities. This has a detrimental effect on SMEs performance since it becomes problematic for them to persuade suppliers, tax authorities, creditors, among others, that their business operations have been regularly monitored by an autonomous or impartial professional. Eyo (2025) utilised multi-regression model, descriptive statistics, and survey data to show that taxation has positive significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth. Olaniyi et al. (2024) adopted time series data and causality test to demonstrate that there exist dissimilar impacts of various taxations on economic performance of Nigeria, with VAT and CIT significantly impacting growth, and a bidirectional causality existing between PIT and growth.

Foreign similar studies have also either examined how tax compliance, tax auditing, tax administration, or taxation among small businesses impacts profitability, performance, or growth of their businesses but have not simultaneously looked at the impact of auditing and taxation on small and medium scale business. For instance, Ndlovu and Schutte (2026) used survey data and qualitative method to analyse in Gauteng, South Africa, how small businesses comply with tax policies. It was discovered by the study that owners of small enterprises in South Africa do not have the required basic tax information that would encourage them to be tax compliant. Again, small businesses were found to be more susceptible to tax dishonesty when likened to other taxpayer clusters. It was recommended among others that government need to make the tax process easy to enable small businesses adequately to comply with tax policies in the economy. Scholtz and Laing (2024) examined how tax compliance could form burden to SMEs in South Africa using descriptive statistics and secondary data from 2023

South African Revenue Services tax report. It was found that SMEs are significantly experiencing tax regulatory challenge or burden and significant high tax compliance cost in the economy. This is because, these firms are always faced inadequate informed staff with requisite skills and knowledge that would help them manoeuvre intricate tax guidelines in a bid to carry out all their tax responsibilities in full and on time. The study suggested among others that that there is need for the government and its tax agencies to indulge in tax regulatory reviews and sometimes grant these SMEs tax incentives to help them grow their businesses in order to transition from informal sector businesses to formal businesses.

Another study by Marivate (2024) used descriptive statistics and secondary data to argue that granting SMEs tax incentives could open ways for their growth and as such, make them transition to larger industries. It was suggested that government should provide all-encompassing grant or assistance through loans, tax incentives, subsidies, and even government partnership investment in the SMEs, especially those that indulge in manufacturing of new energy vehicles. Wadesango and Chirebvu (2020) adopted survey data collected from 50 managers and owners of SMEs and descriptive statistics to ascertain what influences VAT compliance, find out the best techniques for collecting VAT, ascertain how VAT affects business profits and processes, and characterize the state of VAT compliance amidst SMEs in advanced economies. Findings showed that individual traits, aspects of the VAT system itself, and external influences like the political and socioeconomic climate of the advanced economies had major significant influence on VAT compliance. Most SMEs use non-compliance as a strategy to get through the difficult economic times. For SMEs, the costs of putting in place a complicated system are so exorbitant that any attempt to comply is likely to result in the small business's demise. Using similar data and methodology, Wadesango and Khashane (2021) discovered while trying to find out how taxation influences SMEs performance, that tax rises have negative significant impact on SME performance by lowering investment incomes. In another related study, Lepheana (2020) also employed survey data, systematic literature review method, and descriptive statistics to establish what influence taxation could have on small medium and micro business continuity of in South Africa. It was therefore found that in South Africa, taxation negatively and significantly influence small medium and micro business continuity.

Buthelezi (2023) in similar study utilised survey data obtained from tax practitioners and SMEs in Central Business District of Durban, South Africa, and employed descriptive statistics and quantitative method to analyse how tax compliance weight influence SMEs. It was indicated that the burden or weight of tax compliance significantly encourages SMEs failure and strongly discourage their growth and performance. High taxation was discovered to be significantly encouraging SMEs tax noncompliance, thus making them to underreport their profits. As a result of this, significant number of them prefer to remain in informal rather than the formal sector. It was suggested therefore that in order to reduce the costs or burden of tax compliance, there is need for government and its tax agencies to reduce taxation levied on SMEs, encourage electronic tax payment and filing, and train SMEs on how to keep appropriate financial records and how to perform electronic tax filing. Dixon, Smulders, and Odendaal (2024) also tried to examine the costs or weights of tax compliance in South African small, medium and micro businesses using online survey data obtained from registered SMEs in the country and applying quantitative analytical method and descriptive statistics. It was demonstrated by the study that high costs or weights have detrimental impact on small, medium and micro businesses and the economy. Lesejane (2021) also studied in South Africa how costs of tax compliance impact small, medium and micro businesses through the adoption of systematic literature review and descriptive statistics. It was discovered that low earnings, high taxation, non-recordkeeping, lack of tax knowledge and administration were significant barriers influencing small, medium

and micro businesses’ compliance with tax. Hence, favourable and decent taxation were recommended to be levied particularly on small, medium and micro businesses.

Asiimwe (2023) in a related study tried to determine in Uganda how taxation influence SMEs efficiency using survey data and descriptive statistics. It was therefore established that high taxation significantly and negatively influences SMEs performance, competitiveness, and growth. Mba, Ayeni, and Touray (2025) employed time series data and ARDL model to discover that in the short and long run, there exist substantial influence of fiscal policy rate on economic growth in Gambia, with gross fixed capital formation exerting significant reverse influence on the growth of the country. It is worthy to note here that none of these reviewed studies has actually looked at how auditing and taxation has impacted small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria simultaneously. Therefore this study tries to close this study gap through the adoption of a current, comprehensive national or country-wide enterprise survey that focus on small and medium scale businesses and/or firms in all the 36 States of Nigeria and the FCT, and through the application of econometric model with instrumental variable two stage least squares (IV – 2SLS) model as a robustness check.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Theoretical Framework

This study’s theoretical framework is anchored on the agency-deterrence integration theory, which states that auditing should implemented to encourage small and medium scale business performance through the enhancement of financial transparency and accountability (agency), such that auditing and taxation threats deter non-compliance, thereby reducing performance costs that are tied to the penalties and/or reputational damage (Allingham & Sandmo, 1972; Slemrod, 2019). In fact, the theory is of the view that auditing and taxation make small and medium scale businesses to be more effective and compliant, thereby creating room for performance enhancement. The model takes into account the effects of auditing, rates of taxation, evasion fines, and the likelihood of being discovered by tax agencies (Sandmo, 2005; Coolidge, 2012; Slemrod, 2019).

In view of this model, this study specifies the functional form of the agency-deterrence integration theory with respect to the factors that influence small and medium scale business performance as can be seen in equation (1) below:

$$smbp = f \left(\begin{array}{l} \text{aud, taxrt, ownership, managment accountability,} \\ \text{financial information, capital available,} \\ \text{tax administration, institutional regulation} \end{array} \right) \quad (1)$$

where the variables are defined as:

smbp = small and medium scale business performance

aud – auditing of small and medium scale businesses

taxrt = tax rate levied on small and medium scale businesses

ownership = ownership structure of small and medium scale business (i.e. domestic or foreign)

management accountability = management accountability of the small and medium scale businesses

financial information = information of the financial strength of the small and medium scale businesses

capital available = financial resources accessible to the firm, encompassing both internally generated funds and externally sourced financing

tax administration = tax administration being faced by the small and medium scale businesses
 institutional regulation = institutional regulations faced by the small and medium scale businesses.

From the functional form of the agency-deterrence integration theory, this study moves to specify its model specifications as can be seen in the subsequent subsection.

3.2 Model Specifications

This study first specifies the functional form of its estimable model following the agency-deterrence integration theory as it affects small and medium scale business performance. The variables of the estimable functional model of this study are informed based on the World Bank (2025) enterprise survey data. From this survey data, variables that align with theory were selected for the study analysis. Hence, the functional form of the estimable model is specified as can be seen in equation (2) below:

$$smbp = f \left(\begin{matrix} aud, taudm, audrp, taxrt, txadm, inctx, sstax, vatrf, \\ own dico, ownfico, mgtreg, cusreg \end{matrix} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where the variables are defined as presented in Table 1 given below:

Table 1: Model Variable Definitions

Variables	Variable Codes	Definition	
smbp	d2	The establishment’s total annual sales in the last fiscal year (proxy for small and medium scale business performance).	
aud	k21	Financial statements checked & certified by external auditor in last fiscal year (proxy for auditing).	
taudm	j32	Did any of these visits or meetings consist of a tax audit? (proxy for tax audit participation)	
audrp	j33	Weeks until final audit report was received (proxy for tax audit)	Tax variables
taxrt	j30a	How much of an obstacle: Tax rates	
txadm	j30b	How much of an obstacle: Tax administrations	
inctx	n11	Effective income-based tax rate	
sstax	n2a2	Social security payments and employment-based taxes	
vatrf	j39	Weeks to receive VAT refund	
owndico	b2a	% Owned by private domestic individuals, companies or organizations (proxy for ownership)	
ownfico	b2b	% owned by private foreign individuals, companies or organizations (proxy for ownership)	
mgtreg	j2	what % of senior management time was spent in dealing with govt regulations? (management variable)	
cusreg	d30b	How much of an obstacle: Customs and trade regulations? (proxy for institutional regulation)	

Source: Authors’ compilation as extracted from World Bank (2025) Nigerian Enterprise Survey data

Further, the study goes more to specify the mathematical form of its estimable model as presented in equation (3) seen as follows:

$$smbp = \left[\begin{array}{l} b_0 + b_1 aud + b_2 taudm + b_3 audrp + b_4 taxrt + b_5 txadm + b_6 inctx + b_7 sstax \\ + b_8 vatrf + b_9 owndico + b_{10} ownfico + b_{11} mgtreg + b_{12} cusreg \end{array} \right] \quad (3)$$

where the variables remained as defined above in Table 1, b_0 represents the constant term, $b_{1,2,\dots,12}$ stands for the coefficients of the model variables.

In addition to the above, this study also specifies the econometric form of its estimable model as given in equation (4) below:

$$smbp = \left[\begin{array}{l} b_0 + b_1 aud + b_2 taudm + b_3 audrp + b_4 taxrt + b_5 txadm + b_6 inctx + b_7 sstax \\ + b_8 vatrf + b_9 owndico + b_{10} ownfico + b_{11} mgtreg + b_{12} cusreg + \mu \end{array} \right] \quad (4)$$

where the variables remained as defined above in Table 1, μ represents the error term.

Further, in a bid to carry out robustness check in case of any potential endogeneity between businesses being audited ($aud/k21$) and their performance (total annual sales, $smbp/d2$), the study implements IV-2SLS model. Hence, the first stage regresses aud on the instrument(s) and full set of control variables, whereas the second stage estimates business performance ($smbp$) on the predicted value of aud together with the same control variables as specified below:

Stage 1:

$$aud_i = \left[\begin{array}{l} b_0 + b_1 taudm_i + b_2 audrp_i + b_3 taxrt_i + b_4 txadm_i + b_5 inctx_i + b_6 sstax_i + b_7 vatrf_i \\ + b_8 owndico_i + b_9 ownfico_i + b_{10} mgtreg_i + b_{11} cusreg_i + \mu_i \end{array} \right] \quad (5)$$

Stage 2:

$$smbp_i = \left[\begin{array}{l} b_0 + b_1 \widehat{aud}_i + b_2 taudm_i + b_3 audrp_i + b_4 taxrt_i + b_5 txadm_i + b_6 inctx_i + b_7 sstax_i \\ + b_8 vatrf_i + b_9 owndico_i + b_{10} ownfico_i + b_{11} mgtreg_i + b_{12} cusreg_i + e_i \end{array} \right] \quad (6)$$

where, $taudm$ and $audrp$ represents the instruments for aud . \widehat{aud}_i represents first-stage regression predicted value. These instruments were chosen on theoretical grounds to satisfy the relevance (correlation with aud) and exogeneity (influencing business performance through aud). However, the interest here is just to use the IV-2SLS as robustness checks to the robust OLS model.

3.3 Data and Sources

This study's data is sourced from the World Bank (2025) enterprise survey data. This survey data captures many enterprise characteristics that form the business environmental factors of SMEs. It captured firm – level data on auditing, taxes, management practices, regulations, finance, trade, infrastructure and climate, labour, informality, dispute resolution, gender, crime, innovation and technology, corruption, competition and public procurement, and perceptions about doing business obstacles in Nigeria. This survey data population for Nigeria is 1043 businesses gotten from manufacturing, construction, service, and the transportation sectors. As a result of the extreme values of total annual sales (proxy for small and medium scale business performance – $smbp$) and social security payments and employment-based taxes ($sstax$) as evidenced in the descriptive statistics results, these variables were transformed to their logarithmic forms in order to rescale them.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

The study first examines the characteristics and nature of the model variables utilising descriptive statistics. This discloses the key features or characteristics of this firm – level survey

data as it concerns auditing and taxation, and small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. The results of the descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2 below:

Table 2: Descriptive Statistic Results

Variables	Data Codes	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
smbp	d2	1043	1.03e+10	1.00e+11	0	2.56e+12
aud	k21	1043	1.551294	0.9932622	0	2
taudm	j32	644	1.326087	1.995922	0	2
audrp	j33	192	2.328125	7.91788	0	50
taxrt	j30a	1043	1.624161	1.3233	0	6
txadm	j30b	1043	1.347076	1.321736	0	6
inctx	n11	1043	8.01534	14.20192	0	100
sstax	n2a2	1016	2.94e+07	4.09e+08	0	1.00e+10
vatrfr	j39	33	1.969697	8.229083	0	30
owndico	b2a	1043	95.41707	18.98579	0	100
ownfico	b2b	1043	4.030681	17.7647	0	100
mgtreg	j2	1043	3.688399	9.627203	0	100
cusreg	d30b	1043	0.9271333	1.535399	0	6

Source: World Bank (2025) Nigerian Enterprise Survey data

Table 2 indicates that small and medium scale business performance (smbp/d2) has 1043 observations with a mean annual sales or performance of approximately ₦10.3 billion, which suggest a substantial average turnover for the sampled businesses. However, the extremely high standard deviation of ₦100 billion, points to a highly heterogeneous sales or performance distribution of among these businesses. The standard deviation result also signifies the existence of a wide dispersion, with vast range (minimum and maximum values) further supporting the wide variance.

On auditing and tax audit variables results, it was shown that with the financial statements being checked and certified by external auditor (aud/k21), total observation is 1043, with a mean of 1.55 (i.e. categorical variable on a 0-2 scale: 0 = don't know, 1 = yes, and no = 2). This implies that a high portion of these sampled businesses engage external auditors, while greater amount of them do not. The standard deviation of approximately 1 implies a fair amount of variation in auditing practices across these businesses, with majority of them not being audited and others fully audited and certified. Further, tax audit visits or meetings (proxy for tax audit participation) (taudm/j32) has 644 observations with fewer responses or lower sample size, suggesting that not all firms were subject to tax audit visits or meetings. It has a mean of approximately 1.33 and a standard deviation of 1.996, implying that while some firms faced tax audits, many others did not, or the tax audit visit intensity varied significantly among these businesses. The variable on weeks until final audit report was received (audrp/j33) has a smaller observations of 192, signifying that only a subset of firms that underwent audit provided the report on the time taken to receive the final report. It has a mean of approximately 2.33 weeks, implying therefore that on the average, audit reports are received relatively quickly. It has a high standard deviation of about 7.92 weeks, and this means that there exists extreme variability in reporting times.

For taxation, the tax rates perception as obstacle (taxrt/j30a) has an overall observation of 1043, a mean of approximately 1.62 with a standard deviation of 1.32, thereby suggesting that there is a reasonable spread in opinions of these businesses on taxation. Hence, while some view tax rates as being a minor obstacle, others perceive it as being a severe impediment to their businesses. On tax administration (txadm), total observation is 1043, the mean is 1.35, and the

standard deviation is 1.32, hence signifying a considerable level of dispersion. This means therefore that some firms experience smooth tax administrative interactions while others face significant administrative hurdles or challenge. Effective income-based tax rate (inctx/n11) has an overall observation of 1043, with a mean of approximately 8.02% and standard deviation of 14.20. The wide dispersion indicates substantial variations in the actual tax burden faced by these businesses. The Social security payments and employment-based taxes (sstax/n2a2) have a total observation of 1016, with a mean payment of approximately ₦29.4 million, and a standard deviation of about ₦409 million, hence implying that there exists extreme variability in these payments across these businesses. Further, value added tax (VAT) (vatrf/j39) revealed a very limited number of observations (33), with a mean of approximately 1.97, and a high standard deviation of 8.23, thereby suggesting that there exists substantial variation in the VAT refund.

On ownership variables, the descriptive results show that the percentage owned by private domestic individuals, companies or organizations (owndico/b2a) has 1043 observations, with an average (mean) of about 95.42% ownership by private domestic entities, and a relatively low standard deviation of approximately 18.99%, indicating therefore, that a significant majority of these businesses have a very high proportion of domestic ownership, reinforcing higher level of local investments in these businesses. Again, the percentage owned by private foreign individuals, companies or organizations (ownfco/b2b) revealed that the overall observation is 1043, with a quite low mean of just 4.03%, and a standard deviation of 17.76%, hence demonstrating a wide variation in the sample. The results suggest that foreign investment is minimal, reflecting mainly the barriers to foreign entry to small and medium scale businesses.

On management accountability variable, the percentage of senior management time spent on dealing with government regulations (mgtnreg/j2) has a total observation of 1043, with the mean showing that senior management in Nigerian small and medium scale businesses spend approximately 3.69% of their time dealing with government regulations. It has a standard deviation of 9.63% signifying that there exists a wide variance in the sample. This suggests therefore that as some of these businesses' senior management might be spending minimal time dealing with government regulations, a substantial percentage of them commit significant, and even, overwhelming amount of time to deal with regulatory compliance. Institutional regulation variable (the obstacle customs and trade regulations) (cusreg/d30b) revealed an overall observation of 1043, with a mean of approximately 0.93, and standard deviation of 1.54. This implies that there is enough variability in the sample, and at the same time suggests that customs and trade regulations pose a very severe obstacle, especially on those businesses that engage in international trade.

4.2 Regression Results

The study presents the econometric regression results based on the robust Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model technique. The IV-2SLS model is used as a robustness check to the robust OLS results, thereby helping to address potential endogeneity issues in the model. The results are presented as shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Regression Results (Dependent Variable = smbp)

Variables	Data Codes	Robust OLS Model	IV – 2SLS Model
aud	k21	0.435386*** (0.062211)	0.445981*** (0.107810)
taudm	j32	0.210554***	0.246021***

		(0.039121)	(0.051228)
audrp	j33	-0.214765** (0.091240)	-0.403263** (0.142109)
taxrt	j30a	-0.713932*** (0.150391)	-0.491389*** (0.115001)
txadm	j30b	-0.424189*** (0.102921)	-0.541332** (0.172092)
inctx	n11	-0.883821** (0.236812)	-0.611233*** (0.116084)
sstax	n2a2	-0.378377** (0.122922)	-0.509510** (0.164095)
vatrf	j39	-0.736852** (0.266320)	-0.866785* (0.426609)
owndico	b2a	0.658550** (0.203501)	0.798223** (0.322721)
ownfico	b2b	0.506026*** (0.071081)	0.800133** (0.107208)
mgtreg	j2	0.339868*** (0.019408)	0.291289** (0.114241)
cusreg	d30b	-0.110770** (0.016209)	-0.322635** (0.126011)
_cons		0.675632** (0.231310)	-0.433521** (0.201130)

Note: *** = 1% significance level, ** = 5% significance level, and * = 10% significance level. Standard errors are in parenthesis.

Source: World Bank (2025) Nigerian Enterprise Survey data

Table 3 indicates that in the robust OLS model results for when financial statements are checked and certified by external auditor (aud/k21), the coefficient is 0.435386 and this is statistically significant at 1% level of significance. This implies that when the small and medium scale businesses are audited (that is, their financial statements are checked and certified by an external auditor), it would significantly bring about higher performance by approximately 43.54%. This result is consistent with the result of the IV-2SLS model with the coefficient of 0.445981, implying that improvements in the checking and certification of financial statements of small and medium scale businesses by an external auditor would significantly bring about 44.60% increase in their performance. The consistency in both the sign and statistical significance, along with a very similar coefficient magnitudes in both models suggests that the positive significant influence of auditing on small and medium scale businesses performance is robust. This finding supports the agency theory, in which auditing helps to reduce information gap or asymmetry and agency costs, hence leading to the enhancement of firm profitability, access to resources, and as such, significantly drive their performance. Studies by Agbaje *et al.* (2017), Kings (2018), and Olasupo *et al.* (2016) also found similar significant positive impact of auditing on SME performance and growth in Nigeria, hence supporting this study's finding.

For tax audit visits or meetings (taudm/j32), it was found that in the robust OLS model, tax audit participation (taudm) coefficient is 0.210554, and it is statistically significant at 1% level of significance. This indicates that small and medium scale businesses that experience more tax audit visits or meetings tend to have higher performance by about 21.06%. The IV-2SLS model turned out similar result and as such, consistent and robust with the OLS model's

finding, however, it has a coefficient of 0.246021 and significant at 1% level as well. The implication of this result is that small and medium scale businesses that experience more tax audit visits or meetings tend to have higher performance by about 24.60%. This positive and statistically significant influence of tax audit visits or meetings consistency across these models implies that in Nigeria, small and medium scale business involvements in tax audit visits or meetings significantly encourage higher performance among them. In other words, more productive businesses are more likely to indulge in tax audit visits or meetings, since the discipline imposed on them by tax auditing would encourage them to have better financial management and, as a result, higher performance. This finding is in consonance with the views of Kings (2018), and Inegbedion and Okoye-uzu (2024) who believed that even as tax audits are naturally burdensome, it has the capability of enforcing financial discipline and transparency on these businesses, and this would indirectly bring about improved profitability and performance.

Again, a look at one of the tax variables shows that the number of weeks spent until final audit report was received ($\text{audrp}/j33$) shows that in the robust OLS model, it has a negative and statistically significant coefficient (-0.214765) at 5% level of significance. This by implication means that the longer the waiting period for the final audit report, the lower the performance of small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria would be influenced by about 21.48%. This negative significant result is not surprising since it is expected that any delay in receiving audit reports, there is tendency that timely compliance processes, decision-making, and even access to finance would be hindered. This result is consistent with the IV-2SLS model, but with a significant coefficient (-0.403263) at 5% significance level. This suggests that there is about 40.33% significant negative influence of any delay in receiving audit reports on these businesses. Therefore, the consistent negative and significant influence of the number of weeks spent until final audit report are received on the performance of small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria indicates that the result is robust. Hence, the implication of this finding is that timely audits have the tendency to encourage operational efficiency, whereas untimely audits have the potential to discourage performance of these businesses. This finding is consistent with the findings in tax administration literature, which revealed that having effective auditing processes is very vital in enhancing businesses performance growth with the reverse being the case for ineffective auditing processes (Coolidge, 2012; Wadesango & Khashane, 2021).

Further on taxation, it was found in the robust OLS model that perceiving tax rates ($\text{taxrt}/j30a$) as an obstacle by the small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria revealed a negative and statistically significant association with a coefficient of -0.713932 at 1% level of significance. The implication of this result is that a higher perception of tax rates as an obstacle to Nigerian small and medium scale businesses is associated with about 71.39% significant fall their performance. In other words, an increase in perceived severity of tax rates as an obstacle to Nigerian small and medium scale businesses is associated with a 71.39% decrease in their performance and/or total annual sales. This negative significant outcome is not surprising since it is expected that with high tax rates, small and medium scale businesses would be faced with a fall in profitability and retained earnings available for reinvestment, and fall in productivity, thereby impeding growth and performance of these businesses. This finding is robust and consistent with the IV-2SLS model, which also demonstrated a negative significant coefficient (-0.491389) at 1% significance level. This therefore suggests that higher perception of tax rates as an obstacle to Nigerian small and medium scale businesses is associated with about 49.14% significant fall their performance. These significant results further emphasise the views shared by scholars like Asiimwe (2023), Chimenka, *et al.* (2025), Enang, Alexander, and Faley

(2022), Nnam, *et al.* (2022), Olayeye (2025), and even support the positive accounting theory of Watts and Zimmerman (1986).

It was found with respect to the obstacle of tax administrations (txadm/j30b) that its coefficient is significant and negative in both models (-0.424189 in OLS and -0.541332 in IV-2SLS) at 1% and 5% level of significance. This outcome implies that when tax administrations are seen as imposing higher obstacle, the performance of small and medium scale businesses falls by about 42.42% or 54.13% as shown by both models. This negative significant result is not surprising since it is expected that any time tax administration becomes burdensome to these businesses, it would definitely make the compliance costs to rise, and this would result in resource diversion. The result of the OLS model is robust and consistent with that of the IV-2SLS model which reinforces the finding at the 5% significant level. This finding agrees with the economic deterrence theory of Allingham and Sandmo (1972), in which administrative issues or burdens act as an impediment or disincentive to growth, and as such, hamper and/or discourage performance. The finding of this study with respect to tax administration reinforces the views expressed in the studies by Coolidge (2012), Agbaje *et al.* (2017), Slemrod (2019), Lepheana (2020), Lesejane (2021), Dixon, Smulders, and Odendaal (2024), and Scholtz and Laing (2024) who revealed that cumbersome tax frameworks and tax administration burden act as barriers to business growth.

Effective income-based tax rate (inctx/n11) result was shown to have robust and consistent significant negative impact on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria in both the robust OLS and the IV-2SLS models at 5% and 1% levels of significance respectively. It has a coefficient of -0.883821 in the robust OLS model and -0.611233 in IV-2SLS model. The results show that a more effective income-based tax rate has the tendency of decreasing small and medium scale business performance significantly by about 88.38% and/or 61.12% as indicated by both models. In other words, the consistent negative and increased significance in the robustness check confirm that increased effective income-based tax rates would significantly pose a detrimental impact on the performance small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria, maybe through reduction in retained earnings available for reinvestment and growth, hence impeding investment, growth possibilities, and performance of these businesses. This finding is in consonance with economic theory and even agrees with the studies by Asiimwe (2023), Enang, Alexander, and Faleye (2022), Nnam, *et al.* (2022), and Olayeye (2025).

Social security payments and employment-based taxes (sstax/n2a2) revealed that in the robust OLS model, the coefficient is negative significant (-0.378377) at 5% significance level. Again, in the IV-2SLS model, the coefficient remained consistently negative and significant (-0.509510) at 5% level of significance. This shows that the result is robust and consistent. Therefore, these outcomes imply that increased social security payments and employment-based taxes have negative significant association with small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria by about 37.84% and/or 50.95% as demonstrated by both models. This result is expected since when these taxes are increased, labour costs will rise, and this has the potential to decrease profitability, reduced wage to labour, and productivity, thereby deterring performance as well. The implication of the negative significant results across the models signifies that when employment-based taxes become high, they would be characterised by significant cost burden, which could drain and/or discourage small and medium scale business profitability, reinvestment, productivity, and hence performance. This finding is consistent with findings by Chimenka, *et al.* (2025), Enang, Alexander, and Faleye (2022), Nnam, *et al.* (2022), among others who were of the view that labour taxes negatively impact businesses.

The results for value added tax (*vatrf/j39*) indicate that in both the robust OLS and IV-2SLS models, the coefficients (that is -0.736852 (OLS) and -0.866785 (IV-2SLS)) are consistently influencing small and medium scale business performance negatively. However, while the robust OLS model result is significant at 5% level of significance, that of IV-2SLS is significant at 10% level. The results therefore imply that higher value added tax payments make small and medium scale business performance to fall significantly by approximately 73.69%, thereby suggesting that higher value added tax is a significant burden on small and medium scale business revenues, which in turn discourages their performance level. This finding is very plausible since value added tax has the tendency of influencing cash flow and pricing strategies, possibly through hampering of sales, profitability, and productivity, which in turn deter performance. This study's finding agrees with the findings from Coolidge (2012), Wadesango and Chirebvu (2020), and Ojo, and Shittu (2023) who established that VAT compliance usually brings about significant financial pressure and/or strain, with increased complexities of VAT deterring business growth.

An examination of ownership variable revealed that the percentage of small and medium scale businesses owned by private domestic individuals, companies or organizations (*owndico/b2a*) has positive significant influence on small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria. The robust OLS model coefficient for this variable is 0.658550 while that of IV-2SLS model is 0.798223. The result is therefore shown to be robust and consistently positive significant at 5% level of significance. The implication of this outcome is that greater percentage of domestic business ownership significantly leads to more business performance by about 65.86% and/or 79.82% as indicated by both models. Put differently, businesses with greater proportions of domestic ownerships tend to experience increased domestic annual sales, which in turn raise their profitability and performance level. In other words, domestic ownership largely promotes and/or boosts small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria approximately by 65.86%. This finding supports the theory and views of Jensen and Meckling (1976) who opined that domestic investment is an important and significant determinant of economic growth. This finding also aligns with the studies by Ugwu and Omeje (2021), and Omeje, Mba, and Rena (2024) who found that ownership structure significantly influences firm performance.

Again, the result on the percentage of businesses owned by private foreign individuals, companies or organizations (*ownfico/b2b*) has positive significant association with small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria, with a coefficient of 0.506026 in the robust OLS model and a coefficient of 0.800133 in the IV-2SLS model. However, while that of OLS is significant at 1% level, that of IV-2SLS is significant at 5% level of significance. This finding is robust and consistent with each other, even after the IV-2SLS model has accounted for potential endogeneity. The results therefore imply that foreign ownerships positively and significantly influence small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. In other words, greater percentage of foreign business ownerships in Nigeria has the tendency of making the performance of these businesses to rise approximately by 50.60%. This finding is expected since this may mean that with greater percentage of foreign-owned businesses in Nigeria, more capital would be invested in the business, more innovation would follow, increased productivity, sales and profitability would be enhanced, thereby leading to a boost in performance of these businesses. This finding agrees with theory as postulated by Fama (1980), also supports the empirical findings by Ugwu and Omeje (2021), and Asimwe (2023) who illustrated that foreign business influence impact enterprise performance.

On management, it was found that the percentage of senior management time spent in dealing with government regulations (*mgtreg/j2*) while trying to maintain accountability and move the business forward indicates that in the robust OLS model, it has a coefficient of 0.339868 but

showed a coefficient of 0.291289 in the IV-2SLS model. While the OLS model result is positively and statistically significant at 1% level of significance, that of IV-2SLS model also has positive significant influence on small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria but at 5% level. These positive significant influence of these model results on small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria are consistent with each other and as such, robust. This therefore implies that when more time is spent by senior management to deal with government regulations, it would significantly encourage small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria by 33.99% approximately. This finding is counter-intuitive since it is expected that increased regulatory burdens would typically deter performance (Eteng, et al. 2025; Ocheni & Gemade, 2015; Udeh, Odion, & Izevbehai, 2022). The reason for this counter-intuitive results could be that more productive or larger businesses, which are usually prone to more regulations, commit more management time trying to ensure there is compliance, and/or trying to address other government regulations (like securing operating licenses, meeting up with specifications, or trying to manoeuvre other intricate policies) proactively. In another vein, it might also be that more of these successful or productive businesses have the requisite assets to manage government regulatory challenges adequately, instead of the regulation itself, thereby driving and/or enhancing performance. This finding supports literature advocating for efficient management systems and regulatory compliance as a way of enhancing operational efficacy of small and medium scale businesses (Alm, 2012; Lesejane, 2021; Endris & Kassegn, 2022).

On institutional regulations faced by the small and medium scale businesses, it was indicated that the obstacle of customs and trade regulations (cusreg/d30b) in the robust OLS model has a negative statistically significant coefficient (-0.110770) at 5% level significance. This result is supported by the IV-2SLS model with consistent negative statistically significant coefficient (-0.322635) at 5% level significance. This means that the result is robust and consistent. The results therefore suggest that greater perception of customs and trade regulations as an obstacle by these businesses, would significantly reduce the small and medium scale business performance approximately by 11.08% and/or 32.26%. This negative significant influence is expected since anytime customs and trade regulations are seen as obstacles to their businesses, the ease of doing business would be low, business environment becomes very risky and unfavourable, cost of doing business rises, prices of raw materials would rise, sales and profit would fall, investment and productivity would fall as well, and as such make the performance of these businesses fall significantly. Again, even businesses that engaged in foreign trade, who essentially face stiff customs and trade regulations, would definitely face significant lower performance. This finding is in consonance with the studies by Endris and Kassegn (2022), Omeje, Mba, and Rena (2024), and Ndlovu and Schutte (2026) who revealed that harsh regulatory obstacles could have detrimental impact on business productivity.

4.3 Correlation Test

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

Variables	smbp	aud	taudm	audrp	taxrt	txadm	inctx
smbp	1.0000						
aud	0.1715	1.0000					
taudm	0.1174	0.2561	1.0000				
audrp	-0.1380	-0.1173	0.3117	1.0000			
taxrt	-0.3560	-0.3985	-0.0475	-0.0848	1.0000		
txadm	-0.4640	-0.3964	-0.3059	-0.2117	0.0217	1.0000	
inctx	-0.3874	0.0492	-0.1100	0.0499	0.0696	0.0557	1.0000
sstax	-0.0919	-0.1142	-0.5887	-0.1358	0.3489	0.4555	0.3794

vatrf	-0.1242	-0.0299	0.3823	0.0893	-0.0645	-0.0518	0.2934
owndico	0.0691	-0.5157	0.1673	0.2182	-0.2554	-0.1475	-0.4338
ownfico	0.1691	0.5157	-0.1673	-0.2182	0.2554	0.1475	0.4338
mgtreg	0.2874	-0.2322	-0.0594	-0.0759	0.0666	0.1285	0.1425
cusreg	-0.2491	0.1386	0.0760	-0.0503	-0.0552	0.4028	0.3748
	sstax	vatrf	owndico	ownfico	mgtreg	cusreg	
sstax	1.0000						
vatrf	-0.1241	1.0000					
owndico	-0.0591	0.1211	1.0000				
ownfico	0.3491	-0.1211	-0.0302	1.0000			
mgtreg	0.2809	0.2480	-0.1506	0.1506	1.0000		
cusreg	0.2452	0.3145	-0.3388	0.3388	0.3763	1.0000	

Source: World Bank (2025) Nigerian Enterprise Survey data

The model variables’ correlation matrix is shown in Table 4. As shown by the table, the coefficient matrix has very modest values and as a result, it suggests that there is no multicollinearity because none of the model variable’s correlation coefficient is greater than 0.7 or below -0.7, which is considered as a threshold for moderate correlation.

4.4 Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) and Heteroskedasticity Tests

VIF is used to examine how much the variance of the estimated regression coefficients is inflated as a result of collinearity with other predictor variables in the model. It is noteworthy here that high VIF shows high degree of multicollinearity, which result to unstable and unreliable regression coefficients. Hence, when VIF has a value of 1, it implies that there is no correlation between the predictor and any other predictors; when it turns out a value between 1 – 5, it is said to be moderately correlated with other predictors. However, a value of VIF between 5 – 10 indicates that the variable is highly correlated with other predictors, while a VIF value greater than 10 (> 10) indicates that the variable is very highly correlated with other predictors. In addition, the “Tolerance” level, which is the reciprocal of VIF (1/VIF) is also reported by STATA , and a low tolerance value of say, below 0.10 or 0.20, implies a multicollinearity problem (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). On the other hand, heteroskedasticity test is utilised to examine whether there is no constant variance of the error terms in the regression model across the independent variables. These results are presented in Table 5 below:

Table: 5: Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) and Tests for Heteroskedasticity

Variables	Variable Codes	VIF	1/VIF	Interpretation	Implication
aud	k21	2.96	0.370940	No correlation	No multicollinearity
taudm	j32	4.12	0.587501	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
audrp	j33	3.67	0.325517	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
taxrt	j30a	4.82	0.920444	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
txadm	j30b	4.75	0.628964	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
inctx	n11	4.15	0.602250	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
sstax	n2a2	3.38	0.482413	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
vatrf	j39	4.75	0.311200	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
owndico	b2a	3.67	0.612897	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
ownfico	b2b	4.57	0.316693	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
mgtreg	j2	4.13	0.320007	No correlation	moderate, acceptable
cusreg	d30b	4.39	0.51556	No correlation	moderate, acceptable

Mean VIF		4.81		No correlation	moderate, acceptable/ no multicollinearity
Heteroskedasticity Test	chi2(1)	Prob > chi2			
	0.45	0.5031	No heteroskedasticity	Presence of homoskedasticity	

Source: World Bank (2025) Nigerian Enterprise Survey data

Table 5 shows that all VIFs roughly lie between 3 and 5, which is within the acceptable range for multicollinearity among scholars, since none of the variables has a VIF that exceeded the common concern thresholds (i.e. $VIF > 10$). Again, the lowest tolerance ($1/VIF$) values are around 0.31–0.37 for some variables, which is greater than 0.10 or 0.20. The mean VIF (4.81) indicates that, on average, multicollinearity in the model is not a significant concern. Regarding the VIF results therefore, the study concludes that multicollinearity is not a substantial problem in the regression model, and as such, the estimated coefficients are unlikely to be unduly influenced by high correlations among the independent variables. Hence, the coefficient estimates remain unbiased.

On heteroskedasticity, the null hypothesis is that homoskedasticity is present, which implies that the variance of the error term is constant. The results indicate that the p-value for this test is 0.5031, which is much greater than the conventional 5% and 10% significance levels (that is insignificant). Hence, since the p-value (0.5031) exceeds 0.05, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity, thereby, implying that there is no statistically significant evidence of heteroskedasticity in the model at the 5% level of significance.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examined the impact of auditing and taxation on the performance of small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria, utilising World Bank 2025 firm-level data for Nigeria and applying robust OLS model, with IV-2SLS regression model as a robustness check. The findings revealed robust and consistent model results of the determining factors, with both auditing and taxation variables significantly influencing small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. Auditing and tax audit visits or meeting consistently showed positive and statistically significant influence on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. Further, delays in receiving final audit reports were found to be significantly and negatively associated with small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. Taxation-connected variables basically showed robust and consistent negative significant influence on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. In other words, tax rates and tax administrations perception as significant obstacles to these businesses were revealed to be reducing small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria by approximately 71.39% and 42.42% respectively. In addition, greater effective income-based tax rates, social security payments and employment-based taxes, and value added tax were revealed to have negative significant influence on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria by approximately 88.38%, 37.84%, and 73.69% respectively, mostly by raising labour costs, decreasing profitability and cash flows. Ownership structure was also found to have played significant role in encouraging small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria. Both domestic and foreign ownerships were found to have positive significant influence on small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria approximately by 65.86% and 50.60% respectively. Further, increased management time spent dealing with government regulations was shown to have positive significant influence on small and medium scale business performance in the country. However, customs and trade regulations perceptions as obstacle was found be influencing small and medium scale business performance in Nigeria negatively and significantly.

From the study's empirical findings, the policy recommendations of the study include:

1. Enhance and simplify auditing procedures: government and its tax authorities (Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS), and even the Local Government Revenue Authorities) need to boost and incentivise small and medium scale business to undergo routine external audits. This can be done through provision of subsidies for audit services, conducting training programmes on standard financial recording, and/or streamlining audit conditions especially for smaller businesses. Again, regulatory agencies or tax authorities should endeavour to shorten the time it takes for audit reports to be issued, including imposing more stringent deadlines on auditors and putting in place digital channels for quicker report submission and processing.
2. Reassess tax audit systems: although tax audits are sometimes seen as punitive by these businesses, the positive relationship between tax audits and small and medium scale business performance indicates that they may unintentionally promote financial discipline. Hence, tax agencies or tax authorities (Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS), and even the Local Government Revenue Authorities) ought to think about changing the emphasis on tax audits from only punitive actions to one that is more encouraging and instructive. This might entail offering these businesses advice on best practices for tax compliance during auditing, thereby turning audits into educational and development opportunities instead of only enforcement.
3. Taxation and its administration need to be reformed: there is need for urgent government reform of tax policies and tax administration guidelines since both tax rates and tax administration were found to be consistent significant obstacles that impact small and medium scale business performance. This can be done by reviewing and ensuring that existing tax law is equitable, progressive, and does not disproportionately impact these businesses. Therefore, there is need to keep the tax laws simplified, keep the tax burden low, and increase the effectiveness, transparency, and/or openness of tax administration procedures. Easily navigated online tax portals could be created by tax authorities (Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS), and even the Local Government Revenue Authorities) with clear established instructions, and easily accessible support services, to help decrease meaningfully the compliance costs and bring about more favourable climate for small and medium scale business.
4. Lessen the impact of employment, income-based, and VAT taxations: with respect to new and struggling businesses, there is need for government and its tax authorities (Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS), and even the Local Government Revenue Authorities) to grant them tax holidays, lower tax rates, and/or provide simpler tax administrations. Again, lessening of the costs or burdens of employment or job-based taxes, like short-term incentives or subsidies for workers or streamlined social security contribution procedures, may boost employment and business performance.
5. Encourage both strategic foreign investment and domestic ownership: there is need for government and its tax authorities (Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), State Internal Revenue Services (SIRS), and even the Local Government Revenue Authorities) to encourage foreign investment and local entrepreneurship ownerships, through support for indigenous businesses and provision of favourable investment climate. Foreign investments could be tailored to sooth local supply chains through cultural and regulatory direction just to ensure that foreign investments support the national development goals that would enhance local business performance.

6. Based on the findings from management time spent on regulations, customs and trade regulations, there is urgent need for government and its tax agencies, customs, and even the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade & Investment to provide a more efficient and transparent regulatory environment. The priorities of these policymakers should be to streamline the regulatory processes, and plummet bureaucratic red tape. Again, there is urgent need for streamlining of import and export processes, cut down delays, and fight corruption easily seen in customs and trade regulations.

6. LIMITATIONS AND AREAS OF FUTURE STUDIES

The study's findings were based on cross-sectional survey data of World Bank 2025 for Nigeria and as such, were interpreted as associations rather than causal effects and/or causality. Whereas the study employed the robust OLS model and presented IV-2SLS model as robustness checks, the approach assumed that all relevant variables were included in the model. However, small scale business performance may be influenced by many other factors that are often unobservable or difficult to measure. Therefore, omitted variable(s)/unobserved confounders, perception bias, measurement error, and reverse causality have the tendency of affecting the results of the study. Consequently, future research utilising longitudinal, experimental, or quasi-experimental designs are needed to establish causality, clarify, and/or support this study's findings. Further studies can examine small and medium business performance by SME categorization, even at regional or cross-country level.

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